

Dry matter (g/hill)

Influence of different moisture regimes on dry matter content of leaf, stem, and panicle.

Effect of amendments on rice harvest index and its relationship with Fe:Mn uptake in sodic soil

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Gypsum, pyrite, and farmyard manure (FYM) are commonly used amendments to reclaim sodic soils. Rice tolerates sodicity and often is recommended as the first crop in reclamation programs.

We evaluated the effect of amendments on harvest index (HI) and ratio of Fe:Mn uptake in rice in a pot experiment at CSSRI, Karnal. The soil was highly sodic with pH 10.6, 96.5% exchangeable sodium, 0.22% organic carbon, 4.2% CaCO₃, CEC 10.9 meq/100 g soil, 20.4% clay, and gypsum requirement of 25 t/ha. Gypsum and pyrite each at rates equivalent to 0, 50, and 100% gypsum requirement were applied alone or combined with 0, 6.25, or 12.5 g FYM/kg soil.

After applying the amendments, the soil was leached with water to remove soluble reaction products. Recommended doses of N (75 ppm) and Zn (20 ppm

ZnSO₄) were applied as urea and zinc sulfate. Pusa 2-21 was planted and grown to maturity.

Treatment results are in the table. HI was lowest in the control, and increased when 50% of the gypsum requirement was applied. If more gypsum was applied, HI declined. Adding FYM increased HI at all gypsum levels, although higher doses began to reduce the index. At equivalent doses, HI for pyrite treatments was generally lower than for gypsum. FYM plus a 50% gypsum requirement dose of pyrite had little effect on HI.

HI increased as Fe:Mn decreased. There was a significant negative correlation between HI and Fe:Mn uptake by

Effect of gypsum, pyrite, and FYM on rice HI, Karnal, India.

FYM (g/kg soil)	HI				
	Control	Gypsum (% gypsum requirement)		Pyrite (% gypsum requirement)	
		50	100	50	100
0	0.20	0.42	0.39	0.46	0.33
6.25	0.30	0.58	0.49	0.46	0.40
12.5	0.39	0.51	0.40	0.47	0.28

iron tanks with automatic irrigation control.

Soil had high moisture holding capacity. NPK was applied at 150 kg/ha. Soil was maintained at 40, 60, 80, or 100% saturation during growth of varieties Century Patna and Nihonbare.

Total dry matter production for both varieties is in the table. Century Patna yielded the highest dry matter at 100% saturation. Panicle weight, except that of Nihonbare at 40% saturation, was more than 40% of total dry matter produced (see figure). □

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straw (see figure); however, the relationship was insignificant for rice grain. □

Relationship between HI and Fe:Mn uptake in rice, Karnal, India.

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